

Molecular Docking Study of Nutraceuticals from Medicinal Plants against COVID-19 by Targeting PL^{PRO} and RdRp

Amrutha Pulagam¹, Murthi Vidya Rani², Rajitha Galla^{3*}, Umakanth Naik Vankadoth⁴,
Umamaheswari Amineni⁵

^{1,2,3} *Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Institute of Pharmaceutical Technology,
Sri Padmavati Mahila Visvavidyalayam, Tirupati-517502, Andhra Pradesh, India*

^{4,5} *Department of Bioinformatics, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Medical Sciences, Tirupati-517502,
Andhra Pradesh, India*

*Correspondence: Galla Rajitha

Abstract

The SARS-CoV-2 infection continues triggering substantial distress to people since 2019. Many research investigations concerning viral pathogenesis regarding the manner in which the virus infects and multiplies within the host have led to converging conclusions. Numerous studies have additionally demonstrated a strong link between ageing, mild inflammation, metabolic disorders and SARS-CoV-2 illness. According to a modest collection of knowledge, nutraceuticals are capable of avoiding viral invasion and can reduce inflammation. Consequently, in this current work, we report a molecular docking analysis for nutraceuticals from diverse plants against SARS-CoV-2 cysteine proteases PL^{PRO} (PDB ID: 7CJM) and RNA dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp, PDB ID: 6M71) which play major role in viral replication. The molecular docking studies showed that chicoric acid (7CJM : -8.617 Kcal/Mol, 6M71: -6.475) and rosmarinic acid (7CJM : -7.925 Kcal/Mol, 6M71 : -8.323 Kcal/Mol) exhibited good docking scores with the selected targets, which were better when compared to that of reference antiviral drugs Remdesivir and Favipiravir. The majority of the nutraceuticals assessed by Qikprop displayed beneficial pharmacological characteristics for human administration.

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2, Nutraceuticals, Molecular Docking, PL^{PRO}, RNA dependent RNA polymerase

I. INTRODUCTION

The cause of COVID-19 is the novel corona virus, or SARS-CoV-2, a significant and lethal species of the Coronavirinae subfamily of the Coronaviridae ^[1]. The two main members of the Coronaviridae family that sporadically cause pneumonia and respiratory syndromes are SARS-CoV (severe acute respiratory syndrome) and MERS-CoV (middle east respiratory disease) ^[2]. Globally, 6,951,677 deaths and 768,237,788 confirmed cases of COVID-19 have been reported to WHO as of July 19, 2023 ^[3]. Even with all the advancements in modern and conventional medicine, many attempts to contain this pandemic had a harmful impact on people's health. As a result, traditional therapy is now more enthusiastic to offer medical services. Furthermore, it's predicted that no less than 25% of all current drugs are derived either directly or indirectly from traditional therapies, mostly as a consequence of the fusion of modern technology with age-old knowledge ^[4]. Active phytoconstituents known as

nutraceuticals were extracted from functional foods, medicinal plants, and dietary supplements having therapeutic characteristics [5]. Some nutraceuticals have been scientifically proven to possess therapeutic efficiency, for example, Rosemarinic acid [6] reported for its antiviral, Herpes simplex treatment, anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic properties and chicoric acid [7] documented to exhibit antiviral, antioxidant, neuroprotective properties. Many natural extracts have been studied for their potential to serve as drug-like compounds against the SARS-CoV-2 proteases, including allicin, curcumin, ginger and many others [8]. Therefore, these nutraceuticals have been chosen to perform this study. Papain-like protease (PL^{pro}), 3-Chymotrypsin-like protease or main protease (3CL^{pro} or M^{pro}), and spike glycoprotein (S-protein) are common proteases of COVID-19 that the FDA granted approval for application in clinical studies [9],[10]. Molecular docking analysis of some natural extracts like curcumin, apigenin, quercetin, rosmarinic acid and many others were performed against M^{pro} [11]. Virtual screening has identified a list of various disorders for which there are FDA-approved drugs that specifically and successfully bind with viral PL^{pro}. However, in order to demonstrate their effectiveness and suitability for usage in humans, these nutraceuticals still require *in vitro*, *in vivo*, and clinical validation [12], [13]. Since the majority of the natural product ligands utilized in the study were found in regularly consumed fruits, vegetables, and condiments, it is anticipated that their utilization as therapeutic candidates will prevent harmful side effects. In order to investigate the antiviral effectiveness of the nutraceuticals against PL^{pro} and RdRp of SARS-CoV-2, we have explored the docking interactions of numerous nutraceuticals with the selected targets and were compared with the well-known antiviral drugs like Favipiravir [14] and Remdesivir [15] in the present work.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Ligand Preparation

The creation of the ligand dataset for the current study involved gathering 233 nutraceuticals from medicinal plants that were said to have antiviral action, among which best docked nutraceuticals are listed further in the study (for complete reference of such efforts please see refs [16-26]). The 3D structures of the selected nutraceuticals were obtained from the PubChem database. Antiviral drugs Remdesivir and Favipiravir were selected to serve as reference with selected targets in this study. Prior to molecular docking studies, the structures of selected nutraceuticals and reference drugs were optimized and energies were minimized by LigPrep with Schrödinger Epik module [27].

B. Receptor Preparation

The 3D co-crystal structure of SARS CoV-2 PL^{pro} in complex with GRL0617 (5-amino-2-methyl-N-[(1R)-1-naphthalen-1-ylethyl]benzamide) (PDB: 7CJM) and SARS-Cov-2 RdRp in complex with cofactors nsp7 and nsp8 (PDB ID: 6M71) were considered in this study to propose SARS-CoV-2 inhibitors through molecular docking studies. From the protein data bank, selected target structures were downloaded. Protein preparation tasks were performed with the protein preparation wizard and prepared prior to docking in order to add hydrogen atoms, adjustment of protonation states for ionizable molecules, bond order

and formal charge correction, expelling atomic clashes and performed other operations that were not part of refinement procedure of X-ray crystal structure. At neutral pH, the protein structure minimization was carried out using the OPLS_2005 force field, by converging the heavy atoms to RMSD of $0.3\text{\AA}$. Using Glide v7.1, a grid box of $10\text{\AA} \times 10\text{\AA} \times 10\text{\AA}$ was generated around the binding site residues of PL^{Pro} and RdRp. Binding site was defined by analyzing co-crystal structures of selected targets, residues were cross validated using PDBsum^[28].

C. Molecular Docking

Docking strategy protocol was used to determine the binding interactions between nutraceuticals and targets. The prepared nutraceuticals were docked into 7CJM and 6M71. The binding affinity between the target and ligands (nutraceuticals and reference drugs) was studied using the grid-based ligand docking with energetic (GLIDE) XP (extra precision) docking technique. Then the prepared ligands were docked into the grid utilizing Monte Carlo-based simulated algorithm minimization approach. Glide Scores (Gscore) and Molecular Mechanics-Generalized Born Surface Area (MM-GBSA) were used to analyse calculations for the binding free energies, affinities, orientation, and ranking of the protein ligand complex utilizing the Prime module of Schrodinger suite 2021-22 that incorporates the OPLS3 force field and VSGB dissolvable model to look through calculations. Docking was performed for identification of the best compounds with good binding affinity and orientation without steric clashes. Ten poses were created for each ligand during XP docking, and the best pose was preserved after post-docking minimization.

D. Prediction of Pharmacological Descriptors and ADME

Selected Nutraceuticals and reference drugs were subjected to QikProp module of Schrödinger suite for prediction of the pharmacological ADME properties. Additionally, SASA and related values were also determined using Schrödinger suite.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, a glide algorithm is used for prediction of interaction between protein and ligand. Docking algorithms predict all possible structures by scoring every structure. The nutraceuticals were docked into the active site of PL^{Pro} and RdRp; based on the binding conformation, Schrodinger generated binding energies for all the molecules.

A. Molecular Docking

Selected nutraceuticals were subjected to molecular docking with PL^{Pro} which is a cysteine protease with multiple functions, like processing of viral polyprotein chain for viral protein maturation, host inflammation responses dysregulation through deubiquitylation, and host type I interferon antiviral immune responses impairment by removal of interferon stimulated gene 15 (ISG15) modifications. GRL0617 competes with ISG15 for the binding site in PL^{Pro}, and blocks the binding of ISG15 to PL^{Pro} thus inhibits viral replication. Ligplot of interactions between PL^{Pro} and GRL-0617 showing that co-crystal ligand formed interactions with Gln 269, Asp 164. GRL-0617 has been shown to inhibit viral replication of SARS-CoV-2. Among all the docked complexes, isomangiferin exhibited good binding affinity with an XP G score -8.983 Kcal/mol ; MM-GBSA score of -

35.686 Kcal/Mol with 7CJM and found to be significant when compared to reference drugs remdesivir and favipiravir (**Table I**). Isomangiferin formed H-bond interaction with the side chain residues of Glu 167, Tyr 264, Tyr 268, Gln 269; and backbone residues of Asp 164 and leu 162. Chicoric acid formed H-bond interactions with side chain residues of Lys 157, Asp 164, Glu 167, and backbone residues of Gly 266 and Gln 269. Digallate formed two H-bond interactions with side chain residues of Thr 301, one H-bond interaction with side chain residues of Arg 166, Glu 167 and backbone residue of Gly 163, Gln 269. Digallate also exhibited Pi-Pi stacking interaction with Tyr 268. Rosemarinic acid exhibited two H-bond interactions with side chain residues of Glu 167, and one with side chain residue of Arg166, Asp 164 and one with backbone residue of Leu 162. Nicotiflorin exhibited H-bond interactions with side chain residues of Lys 157, Asp 164, Glu 167, Tyr 273 and with backbone residues of Asp 164. Reference antiviral drug remdesivir showed two H-bond interactions with side chain residues of Glu 167 and H-bond interaction with side chain residue of Lys 157 and Arg 166. Favipiravir showed one H-bond interaction with backbone residue of Gln 269 and side chain residue of Asp 164 and Tyr 264 (**Fig 1**). Most of the best docked compounds resemble the interactions of co-crystal ligand indicating that these nutraceuticals might have potential to block the ISG15 binding to PL^{pro} thus can inhibit the replication of the virus.

Table I. Docking scores of best docked nutraceuticals and antiviral drugs against PL^{pro}

Nutraceutical	Docking scores with PL ^{pro}	
	XP G score (Kcal/Mol)	MM GBSA (Δ G) (Kcal/Mol)
Isomangiferin	-8.983	-35.686
Chicoric acid	-8.617	-53.569
Digallate	-8.27	-17.704
Rosemarinic acid	-7.925	-49.489
Nicotiflorin	-7.906	-32.726
GRL-0617	-5.96	-68.436
Remdesivir	-6.023	-46.543
Favipiravir	-3.619	-20.793

Figure 1. a) Ligplot of interactions between PL^{pro} and GRL-0617 b) Docking Interactions of PL^{pro} with Isomangiferin c) Docking Interactions of PL^{pro} with Chicoric acid d) Docking Interactions of PL^{pro} with Digallate e) Docking Interactions of PL^{pro} with Rosemarinic acid f) Docking Interactions of PL^{pro} with Nicotiflorin g) Docking interactions of PL^{pro} with GRL-0617 h) Docking Interactions of PL^{pro} with Remdesivir i) Docking Interactions of PL^{pro} with Favipiravir

a)

b) Isomangiferin (-8.983 Kcal/Mol)

c) Chicoric acid (-8.617 Kcal/Mol)

d) Digallate (-8.27 Kcal/Mol)

e) Rosemarinic acid (-7.925 Kcal/Mol)

f) Nicotiflorin (-7.906 Kcal/Mol)

g) GRL-0617 (-5.96 Kcal/Mol)

h) Remdesivir (-6.023 Kcal/Mol)

i) Favipiravir (-3.619 Kcal/Mol)

Molecular docking study was performed to predict the binding affinities of selected nutraceuticals against RdRp. Adenosine analog (Remdesivir) has high affinity for the active site of RdRp of the SARS-CoV-2 and compete with the natural substrates such as ribonucleotides of the RdRp and get incorporated into the growing RNA chain that leads to termination of the RNA replication [29]. Among all the docked complexes, rosemarinic acid exhibited good binding affinity with XP G score -8.323 Kcal/mol and MM-GBSA score -63.0105 Kcal/Mol with RdRp which were better when compared with binding affinities of reference drugs Remdesivir and Favipiravir (**Table II**). Rosemarinic acid formed one H-bond interaction with side chain residue of Glu35. Malabaricone exhibited two H-bond interactions with backbone and side chain residues of Asn 459 and side chain residue of Asn 628 and backbone residue of Thr 394. Baicalin exhibited one H-bond interaction with backbone residue of Phe 396 and Asn 459 and Pi-Pi stacking interaction with Arg 349. Chlorogenic acid exhibited H-bond interactions with side chain residue Thr 394, Asn 459 and Asn 628. Chicoric acid exhibited two pi-pi stacking interactions with Lys 500 and Arg 624, and H-bond interactions with side chain residues Tyr 456 and Ser 501. Reference antiviral drug Favipiravir showed H-bond interaction with the side chain residues of Arg553, Asp 623 and Arg 624. Remdesivir showed three H-bond interactions with side chain residues of Asp 452, Lys 545, Arg 555 and backbone residues of Ser 682 (**Fig 2**). The best docked nutraceuticals exhibited good binding affinities than the reference antiviral drugs indicating that these compounds can terminate RNA replication by inhibiting RdRp.

Table II: Docking scores of best docked selected nutraceuticals and reference antiviral drugs against RdRp

Nutraceutical	Docking Scores with RdRp	
	XP G score	MMGBSA (ΔG)
Rosemarinic acid	-8.323	-63.0105
Malabaricone C	-7.901	-49.8617
Baicalin	-6.953	-60.0771
Chlorogenic acid	-6.273	-45.1754
Chicoric acid	-6.475	-3.44108
favipiravir	-3.149	-4.81583
Remdesivir	-2.324	-43.6073

Figure 2. a) Docking Interactions of RdRp with Rosemarinic acid **b)** Docking Interactions of RdRp with Malabaricone C **c)** Docking Interactions of RdRp with Baicalin **d)** Docking Interactions of RdRp with Chlorogenic acid (-6.425 Kcal/Mol) **e)** Docking Interactions of RdRp with Chicoric acid **f)** Docking Interactions of RdRp with Favipiravir **g)** Docking Interactions of RdRp with Remdesivir

Table III. List of best docked nutraceuticals and reference antiviral drugs, Pubchem ID and structure

Compound name	Pubchem ID	Structure
Isomangiferin	5318597	
Chicoric acid	5281764	
Digallate	54711004	
Rosemarinic acid	5281792	
Nicotiflorin	5318767	
Malabaricone C	100313	
Baicalin	64982	
Chlorogenic acid	1794427	
Favipiravir	492405	

Remdesivir	121304016	
-------------------	-----------	--

B. ADME prediction

The selected nutraceuticals and reference antiviral drugs remdesivir and favipiravir were subjected to Pharmacological descriptors, ADME properties prediction such as Molecular weight (MW); Volume (A^0); Globularity (Glob); Total solvent accessible surface area (SASA); Weakly polar solvent accessible surface area (WPSA); Carbon Pi solvent accessible surface area (PISA); Hydrophobic solvent accessible surface area (FOSA); Ionization potential (IP); Hydrogen bond Donors and acceptors (HBD) & (HBA), Lipinski's Rule of 5 Violations (Rule of 5); Partition coefficient (Log $P_{o/w}$); log BB brain/blood (Log BB); serum protein binding (Log KhSa), skin permeability cm/h(Log KP); Violation of Jorgensen Rule of 3 (Rule of 3) using QikProp module of Schrödinger and values were represented in **Table IV & V**. Results indicated that most of these nutraceuticals exhibited favorable ADME properties within the range of 95% known drugs.

Table IV: Pharmacological descriptors of best docked nutraceuticals and reference antiviral drugs

Nutraceutical	MW	volume	Glob	SASA	WPSA	PISA	FOSA	IP(eV)	HBD	HBA
Isomangiferin	422.34	1114.133	0.843645	616.07	0	134.715	83.82	9.142	7	13
Chicoric acid	474.37	1355.932	0.766397	773.04	0	291.217	46.114	8.941	6	11
Digallate	322.22	895.844	0.842708	533.30	0	157.604	0	9.232	6	8.25
Rosemarinic acid	360.32	1096.181	0.803552	639.84	0	252.932	63.284	8.957	5	7
Nicotiflorin	594.52	1493.899	0.851631	742.09	0	182.986	163.186	9.161	8	19.8
Malabaricone C	358.43	1135.29	0.871907	603.62	0	189.905	227.045	8.858	2	3
Baicalin	446.36	1224.778	0.8058	687.03	0	279.554	66.233	8.706	4	11.55
Chlorogenic acid	354.31	1032.501	0.833317	592.85	0	142.696	120.484	9.312	6	9.65
Favipiravir	157.10	481.446	0.92492	321.18	48.2	60.695	0	9.659	1	4
Remdesivir	602.58	1730.386	0.787994	884.58	0	241.136	375.462	8.605	5	16.65

Table V: ADME properties of best docked nutraceuticals and reference antiviral drugs

Nutraceutical	Log P o/w	Log BB	Log KhSa	Rule of 5	Rule of 3	Log KP
isomangiferin	-1.984	-3.703	-0.879	2	2	-7.507
Chicoric acid	0.888	-5.286	-0.944	2	1	-7.084
Digallate	-0.897	-3.446	-0.954	1	1	-7.12
Rosemarinic acid	1.195	-3.441	-0.563	0	1	-5.537
Nicotiflorin	-2.179	-3.92	-1.141	3	2	-6.828
Malabaricone C	3.883	-1.917	0.452	0	0	-2.947
Baicalin	0.434	-3.422	-0.698	2	1	-6.056
Chlorogenic acid	-0.298	-3.204	-0.931	1	1	-6.133
Favipiravir	-0.436	-1.032	-0.741	0	0	-5.121
Remdesivir	1.271	-3.278	-0.59	2	0	-4.073

IV. CONCLUSION

The current work evaluated the ability of nutraceuticals derived from medicinal plants and foods which form essential elements of cuisines all over the world, to inhibit two crucial SARS-CoV-2 protein targets, PL^{pro} (7CJM) and RdRp (6M71), which are crucial for viral replication. A set of 233 selected nutraceuticals and reference antiviral medications were initially molecular docked with the PL^{pro} and RdRp of SARS-CoV-19. Chicoric acid and rosemarinic acid exhibited good binding affinity to the two selected targets than that of the reference drugs thereby found to be the most effective molecules. Thus, these 2 compounds could serve as promising leads for future research in this area. Further, the findings of the current study provide information regarding how these nutraceuticals may prevent SARS-CoV-2 replication more successfully when PL^{pro} and RdRp are both inhibited simultaneously. Although the results are preliminary, they should be supplemented with more comprehensive dynamic simulation studies to have a better understanding of the method of inhibition. As stated elsewhere, the aim of this article is to draw a conclusion to the potentiality of some of these nutraceuticals, to enthuse the research area about these prospects, and to hopefully stimulate the development of nutraceuticals as potent lead drug molecules against the COVID-19 virus.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. R. Weiss and J. L. Leibowitz, "Corona pathogenesis," *Adv. Virus Res.*, 2011, vol. 81, pp. 85-164.
- [2] E. Wit, D. Doremalenvan, N. D. Falzarano, and V. J. Munster, "SARS and MERS: Recent insights into emerging coronaviruses," *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.*, 2016, vol. 14, pp. 523-534.
- [3] World Health Organization (2023). <https://covid19.who.int/> accessed on 26 July 2022. <https://covid19.who.int/>
- [4] World Health Organization, "Traditional medicine in the WHO South-East Asia Region: review of progress," 2014–2019. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/340393>
- [5] T. Varzakas, G. Zakyntinos, and F. Verpoort, "Plant Food Residues as a Source of Nutraceuticals and Functional Foods," *Foods*, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods5040088>
- [6] E. K. Sally, Y. Ali, M. Sara, H. Aaron, M. Eileen, and A. Elian, "Deciphering the therapeutic potentials of rosemarinic acid," *Scientific Reports, Nature*, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-19735-y>

- [7] G. Ahsas, D. Nandini, A. Anant, S. Rashmi, and V. Aanchal, "An insight into the promising therapeutic potential of chicoric acid," *Curr Pharm Biotechnol.*, 2023. DOI: 10.2174/0113892010280616231127075921
- [8] B. J. Oso, A. A. Oluwaseun, and I. F. Olaoye, "Pharmacoinformatics and hypothetical studies on allicin, curcumin, and gingerol as potential candidates against COVID-19-associated proteases," *J. Biomol. Struct. Dyn.*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07391102.2020.1813630>
- [9] C. Mouffouk, S. Mouffouk, L. Hambaba, and H. Habab, "Flavonols as potential antiviral drugs targeting SARS-CoV-2 proteases (3CLpro and PLpro), spike protein, RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) and angiotensin-converting enzyme II receptor (ACE2)," *Eur. J. Pharmacol.*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2020.173759>
- [10] M. Zmudzinski, M. Rut, G. Olech, J. Granda, and M. Drag, "Ebselen derivatives are very potent dual inhibitors of SARS-CoV-2 proteases -PLpro and Mpro *in vitro* studies," *bioRxiv.*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.08.30.273979>
- [11] Megha Hastantram Sampangi-Ramaiah, Ram Vishwakarma, and R. Uma Shaanker, "Molecular docking analysis of selected natural products from plants for inhibition of SARS-CoV-2 main protease," *Current Science*, 2020, vol. 118(7), pp. 1087-1092.
- [12] D. Shin, R. Mukherjee, D. Grewe, and I. Dikic, "Inhibition of papain-like protease PLpro blocks SARS-CoV-2 spread and promotes anti-viral immunity," *Res Sq.*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2601-5>
- [13] N. Barretto, D. Jukneliene, K. Ratia, Z. Chen, A. D. Mesecar, and S. C. Baker, "The papain-like protease of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus has deubiquitinating activity," *J. Virol.*, 2005, vol. 79(24), pp. 15189–15198.
- [14] Y. Furuta, T. Komeno, and T. Nakamura, "Favipiravir (T-705), a broad spectrum inhibitor of viral RNA polymerase," *Proc. Jpn. Acad. Ser. B. Phys. Biol. Sci.*, 2017, vol. 93(7), pp. 449-463.
- [15] C. J. Gordon, E. P. Tchesnokov, E. Woolner, J. K. Perry, J. Y. Feng, D.P. Porter, and M. Götte, "Remdesivir is a direct-acting antiviral that inhibits RNA-dependent RNA polymerase from severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 with high potency," *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2020, vol. 295(20), pp. 6785-6797.
- [16] J. A. Kuban, K. K. Sahu, M. Gorska, J. A. Tuszynski, and M. Wozniak, "Chicoric acid binds to two sites and decreases the activity of the YopH bacterial virulence factor," *Oncotarget*, 2016, vol. 7(3), pp. 2229-2238.
- [17] S. Yu, Q. Guo, T. Jia, X. Zhang, D. Guo, Y. Jia, J. Li, and J. Sun, "Mechanism of Action of Nicotiflorin from *Tricyrtis maculata* in the Treatment of Acute Myocardial Infarction: From Network Pharmacology to Experimental Pharmacology," *Drug Des. Devel. Ther.*, 2021, vol. 15, pp. 2179-2191.
- [18] V. Swarup, J. Ghosh, S. Ghosh, A. Saxena, and A. Basu, "Antiviral and anti-inflammatory effects of rosmarinic acid in an experimental murine model of Japanese encephalitis," *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 2007, vol. 51(9), pp. 3367-3370.
- [19] D. A. Oliveira, D. Prince, C. Y. Lo, L. H. Lee, and T. C. Chu, "Antiviral activity of theaflavin digallate against herpes simplex virus type 1," *Antiviral Res.*, 2015, vol. 118, pp. 56-67.
- [20] M. S. Zheng, and Z. Y. Lu, "Antiviral effect of mangiferin and isomangiferin on herpes simplex virus," *Chin. Med. J.*, 1990, vol. 103(2), pp. 160-165.
- [21] J. Xu, Z. Xu, and W. Zheng, "A Review of the Antiviral Role of Green Tea Catechins," *Molecules*, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22081337>
- [22] Y. Ding, Z. Cao, L. Cao, G. Ding, Z. Wang, and W. Xiao, "Antiviral activity of chlorogenic acid against influenza A (H1N1/H3N2) virus and its inhibition of neuraminidase," *Sci Rep.*, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep45723>
- [23] V. P. Santhi, P. Masilamani, V. Sriramavaratharajan, R. Murugan, S. S. Gurav, V. P. Sarasu, S. Parthiban, and M. Ayyanar, "Therapeutic potential of phytoconstituents of edible fruits in combating emerging viral infections," *J. Food. Biochem.*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfbc.13851>
- [24] V. Umashankar, S. H. Deshpande, H. V. Harsha, S. Ishwar, and D. Chattopadhyay, "Phytochemical Moieties From Indian Traditional Medicine for Targeting Dual Hotspots on SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein: An Integrative *in-silico* Approach," *Front Med.*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.672629>
- [25] E. Moghaddam, B. T. Teoh, S. S. Sam, R. Lani, P. Hassandarvish, Z. Chik, A. Yueh, S. Abubakar, and K. Zandi, "Baicalin, a metabolite of baicalein with antiviral activity against dengue virus," *Sci.* 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep05452>

- [26] N. Saranya, M. Jayakanthan, C. Ravikumar, A. Kandavelmani, N. Bharathi, N. Kumaravadivel, G. Ramasamy, R. Muthurajan, M. Subbarayalu, and K. Neelakandan, "Exploring Phytochemicals of Traditional Medicinal Plants Exhibiting Inhibitory Activity Against Main Protease, Spike Glycoprotein, RNA-dependent RNA Polymerase and Non-Structural Proteins of SARS-CoV-2 Through Virtual Screening," *Front Pharmacol.*, 2021. doi:10.3389/fphar.2021.667704
- [27] Schrödinger LLC. Schrödinger Software Release; 2015 – 2. Available: http://gohom.win/ManualHom/Schrödinger/Schrödinger_2012_docs/general/qikprop_props.pdf Accessed 6 Sep 2021
- [28] Z. Jin, X. Du, Y. Xu, Y. Deng, M. Liu, Y. Zhao, B. Zhang, X. Li, L. Zhang, C. Peng, Y. Duan, J. Yu, L. Wang, K. Yang, F. Liu, R. Jiang, X. Yang, T. You, and H. Yang, "Structure of M^{pro} from SARS-CoV-2 and discovery of its inhibitors," *Nature*, 2020, vol. 582(7811), pp. 289-293.
- [29] Y. Gao, L. Yan, Y. Huang, F. Liu, Y. Zhao, L. Cao, T. Wang, Q. Sun, Z. Ming, L. Zhang, J. Ge, L. Zheng, and Z. Rao, "Structure of the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase from COVID-19 virus," *Science*, 2020, vol. 368(6492), pp. 779-782.